

Review of: "Hepatitis B virus infection in the Lao PDR: A systematic review"

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Potential competing interests: The author(s) declared that no potential competing interests exist.

The present manuscript is interesting because it systematically reviews the epidemiology of hepatitis B in an Asian country endemic for this disease. The results shown are useful to improve epidemiological knowledge in this area. However, I question and suggest a few points:

- Why was gray literature not investigated?
- Why did only one researcher do the identification and extraction of data? Wouldn't it be ideal for two or three independent researchers to carry out these activities to avoid bias?
- A statistical analysis of the quality of manuscripts selected for review may be important, such as heterogeneity analysis and funnel plot.